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A Study on Reunification of the Korean Peninsula: Focusing on the Perspective of Globalization

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Abstract

After World War II, North and South Korea were split up. This changed the strategic situation on the Korean peninsula and in Northeast Asia. The split, reinforced by the Korean War, left two nations with opposing systems: North Korea's dictatorial communism versus South Korea's democratic capitalism, making reunification extremely challenging. Despite this, both governments have consistently declared reunification a national goal. Efforts such as the 1972 peace talks and South Korea's Sunshine Policy have sought to bridge the divide, and North Korea's membership in the United Nations signals some willingness to engage internationally. Globalisation plays a crucial role in this context. In today's interconnected "global village," no nation is entirely self-sufficient. Economic, technological, and resource interdependence tie countries together—agriculturally rich nations need technology, while technologically advanced nations require agricultural goods. The COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated this interdependence vividly, as the entire world faced a common crisis requiring cooperation across borders. This study aims to examine how globalisation can influence the reunification of the Korean Peninsula, highlighting that in a world of deep interconnections, mutual dependence might pave the way for overcoming ideological and political barriers.

Keywords: North Korea; South Korea; World War II; Globalisation; Sunshine policy.

1. Introduction

Since the end of World War II, the Korean Peninsula has posed difficult questions for the international community. The division of the region along the 38th parallel, drawn hastily by the Soviet Union and the United States as they emerged as global powers, set the stage for decades of uncertainty and conflict. Since then, the peninsula has remained a prominent issue, largely due to North Korea's nuclear program. Scholars have explored potential strategies for denuclearizing the Korean Peninsula, and ongoing efforts have aimed at reconciliation between the two Koreas, but none have yielded significant results. Numerous theories and reunification proposals have been put forward in the past, but they have largely been rhetorical and lacked substance; nothing has effectively moved forward to bring the two Koreas closer to reconciliation.

The Sunshine Policy of President Kim Dae-jung, which was based on liberal international relations theory, represented a modest empirical step toward unconditional engagement aimed at encouraging reform in North Korea. However, it ultimately proved unsuccessful in

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achieving Korean reunification, as North Korea remains psychologically defensive and often adopts a pragmatic stance. Additionally, changes in South Korean government policies influence approaches toward North Korea. Conservatives tend to adopt a strong realist position, emphasizing military preparedness, sanctions, and harsh condemnation of North Korea's military posture. In contrast, progressives and liberals favor a more engaging strategy, believing that diplomatic engagement can influence North Korea's policies regarding the Korean peninsula.

The 21st century is marked by informatization, globalization, openness, and interconnectedness. As a result of globalization, the world has become increasingly borderless, and North Korea's planned economy, based on Juche ideology and self-reliance, has struggled, leading to economic decline and extreme poverty. In this context, globalization plays a significant role. Over the years, it has also influenced both Koreas and their interactions with each other. China, a strong supporter of North Korea, has adopted a liberal economic model that has contributed to its rapid economic growth.

Additionally, the Basic Agreement on Reconciliation, Non-aggression, and Exchanges and Cooperation (1991), along with the Joint Declaration on Denuclearization of the Korean Peninsula (1992), initially made little progress from either side. These agreements aimed to end decades of mutual non-recognition, identify areas for cooperation, and establish an institutional framework for unification. However, they were ultimately characterized by rhetoric that lacked substance. Even with all of these different agreements and attempts, the main problems between the two Koreas were still not solved.

Some researchers and scholars have proposed a variety of theories and new perspectives regarding globalization and its influence on Korea's reunification process. During a time when the world was witnessing superpower reconciliation, European integration, and even the reunification of Germany, the possibility of Korea's own reunification began to seem more realistic. To support this goal, South Korea introduced its "Northern Policy," which sought to build economic and diplomatic ties with socialist nations. Over time, this strategy opened doors to stronger relations with former Soviet satellite states, the Soviet Union, the People's Republic of China, and eventually most members of the Commonwealth of Independent States. By strengthening bonds with North Korea's allies, South Korea hoped to encourage the North to take a more cooperative approach (Johnson, 1993). When considering the German example, it is essential to look at how different social groups, workers, farmers, business

owners, and elites experienced the transformation of their society. In the same way, any study of North Korea must pay close attention to how these groups perceive both the old system and the changes currently unfolding (Hofmann & Martens, 2016).

A closer look at North Korea's evolving social structure is therefore necessary. This includes research into the country's industrial system, political framework, and, importantly, the everyday routines that shape the "system of daily life" for ordinary citizens. As marketization expands and foreign cultural influences spread, the signs of change in daily life are becoming more visible, offering key insights into how North Korean society is gradually transforming (Martens, 2016).

In the same year, Cha comprehensively explained the previous efforts and endeavours regarding the integration of the two Koreas. He gave five major theories of Korean unification: winner takes all, too difficult to dangerous, sunshine policy, pragmatism, and jackpot (Cha, 2016).

A survey involving 500 South Korean respondents, encompassing diverse age groups, genders, political orientations, and educational backgrounds, was conducted to examine public perceptions of Korean reunification. The study sought to assess not only general attitudes toward unification but also preferences regarding the form that reunification should take. According to the survey, the most popular idea for Korean reunification was ending the geographical division on the Korean peninsula (average 57.5%). The most popular type of reunification was setting up a single political system based on South Korea (average 56.9%). The most common reason given for why the two Koreas should reunite was to end the threat of war (average 78.6%), followed by the fact that they are of the same 'Han ethnicity' (average 53.1%). The most common reason given for why unification was to improve North Korea's political and economic situation (average 67.3%; Lee, 2019).

There are a vast number of studies based on the unification of the two Koreas; however, there is a lack of research based on the unification of the two Koreas through globalization.

2. Globalisation as a Driving Force in the Reunification Process

In the last few decades, welfare states around the world have changed in many different ways. Slow economic growth in the industrialized West has made welfare policies a major political battleground between the new Right and the traditional Left. This has led to major changes in Anglo-Saxon and Scandinavian countries. In Eastern Europe, newly

capitalist societies continue to grapple with reshaping the welfare systems they inherited from socialist regimes, while in Latin America, nations facing recurring economic crises treat welfare reform as a central part of their adjustment strategies.

At the heart of these reforms lies neoliberalism, a trend closely tied to globalization and the growing integration of national economies into a global system. Globalization is often seen as pressuring governments to align with market principles, liberalizing trade, lifting capital controls, opening financial markets, and reducing state involvement in the economy. Because welfare systems depend on both state intervention and economic growth, this global shift is frequently portrayed as making the reduction or even dismantling of welfare programs inevitable.

Yet, this view is contested. Critics argue that the impact of globalization on welfare states is overstated, particularly because it underestimates the role of domestic politics. They point out that higher social spending can, in fact, strengthen a country's ability to compete globally, just as earlier phases of capitalist development required government intervention to address inequality and insecurity.

In short, two competing perspectives emerge: one predicts the shrinking of welfare states under globalization, while the other anticipates their resilience or even expansion. Though most of the debate is drawn from the experiences of developed countries, its implications extend globally. As Esping-Andersen observes, neoliberal thinking strongly influences welfare strategies in developing nations, where the traditional social democratic "middle way" is fading. Policy prescriptions often promote privatization models, such as Chile's, over the Swedish welfare state, leading to reduced provisions in many emerging economies. However, critics emphasize that this overlooks real-world variations, noting that in some developing countries, greater globalization is actually associated with stronger welfare activities. The central debate, therefore, remains unresolved: globalization may either weaken or reinforce welfare states, and the outcome depends heavily on political, economic, and social contexts.

This article, however, will not merely argue that globalization has resulted in a greater emphasis on welfare in Korea. Recognizing the dangers of most macrostructural arguments that simply correlate one large-scale phenomenon with another without analyzing the underlying dynamics, this study aims to carefully trace the development of Korea's welfare state since 1997. Additionally, it will explore the conditions under which the seemingly

destructive force of globalization can instead act as a driving force behind the expansion of the welfare state.

3. Globalisation and the Dual Realities of Korea

Korea at the crossroads: economic crisis and scenario

South Korea officially asked the IMF for emergency loans on November 21, 1997, when the Asian financial crisis was at its worst. It had realized it could not meet its debt responsibilities on its own. By late 1997, the Korean won had dropped from 808 won to nearly 2,000 won for every dollar. At the same time, the Central Bank's foreign funds had hit less than \$8 billion. This sharp drop in value caused a very bad recession. Growth dropped from 7.1% in 1996 to -5.8% in 1998, unemployment rose from about 2% to over 8%, and a government that had been known for having sound budgets for a long time now had a deficit of -4.4% of GDP. In short, the Korean economy had gone into a dramatic collapse after decades of very fast progress.

Under the IMF agreement, the government committed to sweeping structural reforms aimed at deregulation and liberalism. These reforms fell broadly into three categories:

1. lifting restrictions on capital flows and foreign ownership to attract overseas investment.
2. Easing rules on layoffs to make labor markets more flexible.
3. Strengthening financial transparency and accountability, including consolidated financial reporting and bans on cross-debt guarantees among chaebols. Collectively, these measures represented a decisive turn toward neoliberal economic reform (Mo & Moon, 1998).

In this context, views on Korea's social welfare policy diverged. From the conventional perspective, expanding welfare was simply unaffordable. To repay debts, revive production, and restore international competitiveness, Korea needed to cut costs, attract investment, and run trade surpluses, not increase social spending. Higher welfare expenditure would raise labor costs, worsen the fiscal deficit, and potentially scare off foreign investors who sought low-cost environments. At most, the government might pursue minimal poverty relief programs, designed in line with neoliberal principles such as privatization, decentralization, means testing, and workfare. By this reasoning, globalization would not expand Korea's

welfare commitments but instead push the country toward a lean, neoliberal welfare model.

Critics, however, offered a different outlook. Functionally, welfare expansion could reduce the risk of unrest, restore stability, and reassure investors about Korea's political and social environment. Politically, leaders had strong incentives to respond to public fear and widespread job insecurity, especially after neoliberal labor reforms weakened protections. In such circumstances, promising stronger safety nets could become both a vote-winning strategy and a stabilizing policy. From this angle, neoliberal reforms and globalization might actually go hand in hand with greater investment in social welfare.

In light of this, what has Korea done since September 1997? While it may still be too early for a final judgment, many scholars agree that Korea has moved steadily toward building a more robust welfare state in the years that followed (Y. Kim, 1999; Chung, 1998).

Social Support System Prior to the Crisis

Before the financial crisis, Korea's social welfare system was shaped by its so-called "miracle economy," which had delivered more than three decades of high growth and low unemployment (Y. Kim, 1998). For most citizens, rising real incomes and steady jobs provided access to essential needs such as healthcare, housing, education, pensions, and even a degree of financial security, reducing the immediate demand for government-led welfare programs. Strong family networks and corporate welfare systems offered additional, though secondary, support. The state itself played only a limited role, covering basic healthcare, industrial accident insurance, and minimal assistance for those without work or family resources. Because of this, Korea's welfare system stayed fairly underdeveloped, even though its economy grew quickly. This was because the government spent more on infrastructure and economic services than on social programs.

Because of rapid income growth and the state's limited commitment to welfare, many Koreans turned to building their own safety nets. By 1997, Korea recorded one of the world's highest gross domestic savings rates at 34.25% of GDP (World Bank, 1999) and ranked second globally in private insurance premium payments, which reached 15.42% of GDP (Korean Economy Daily, August 11, 1999). This reliance on private initiatives rather than public support reflected the priorities of past authoritarian regimes, which emphasized economic growth and political stability over social welfare. Resources were directed to social programs only when they aligned with economic objectives, reinforcing a developmentalist

ideology shared by political elites, technocrats, and chaebols. Their guiding belief was that rapid growth and self-reliance were the best ways to meet social needs (Lee, 1993).

After the democratization movement of 1987, this developmentalist agreement started to weaken. However, it was still important to ruling coalitions and most people still agreed with it. When the economy crashed in late 1997, it was clear how weak it was. Young-hwan Lee wrote in 1998 that social welfare scholars at the time were torn between fear and hope: would the crisis make welfare even smaller because of tight budgets and pressures for neoliberal reform, or would it make it possible to expand by showing where Korea's current safety nets were weak? There was a sense that a new welfare state might be taking shape in the middle of economic chaos because of all the uncertainty.

4. North Korea's Cultural Identity and Education

From antiquity until 1910, Korea employed a Confucian educational approach, which persisted until the Japanese occupation. Knowledge of the Chinese classics was essential for literacy. Although Koreans preserved their unique language and culture, they adopted Confucian social norms and moral values. While Confucianism has been officially rejected in North Korea, some argue that its social principles still influence both North and South Korean societies. The 36-year Japanese occupation remains a painful and vivid memory for people in both Koreas. North Korea relies on financial support from the Korean diaspora in Japan, yet publicly, anti-Japanese sentiments are commonly expressed in newspapers and textbooks.

The concepts of independence and sovereignty were established and articulated by Kim Il-sung, central to the Juche doctrine, which emphasizes Korea's resistance to Japanese occupation. Professor Nam Djin Ou of the Higher Teacher Training College in Pyongyang describes North Korea prior to liberation from Japan as a "semi-feudal colonial nation" with a highly "backward" economy and culture, as discussed in an article on North Korean education. Following the DPRK's liberation, significant progress was made in combating illiteracy. To achieve this, adult schools, evening classes, workshop schools, and Korean alphabet schools were established across the country. North Koreans refer to this period as the "calm building-up phase and democratization of schools and education." During this time, schools also began to exhibit a clear Soviet influence; images of Russian heroes were displayed in classrooms, and teachers encouraged students to "learn from the Soviet Union." Prominent Soviet educators were highly regarded. In terms of globalization and education, instructional materials used at North Korean teachers colleges emphasized figures such as N. K. Krupskaya,

Lenin's wife, and A. S. Makarenko. These sources contributed to the development of the core principles of North Korean education: the integration of theory and practice, and collectivism. The mandatory education system, which had been in place for three years, was fully operational.

Currently, the primary beneficiaries of North Korea's education system are the Republic of Korea to the south and the rest of the world. Kim Il-sung has described the DPRK's education system as the "most sophisticated system of free compulsory education." According to a public statement made in 1993, the state awards each student a bonus of 16,000 won in recognition of the 1950-1953 Korean War, which caused widespread destruction on the Korean Peninsula.

Approximately 90% of all cultural and educational institutions were destroyed, and about 850,000 North American students, roughly half of the total, were enlisted to support the war effort. After the Korean War, several educational reforms were implemented. In 1956, universal elementary education became a reality. Over the next two decades, the system was gradually expanded until 1972, when the 11-year education system was introduced. Between 1972 and 1975, significant developments occurred in the educational sector: 60,000 instructors were trained, government expenditure increased by a factor of 1.7, and an additional 30,000 classrooms were built. By 1975, North Korea's "cradle to grave" education system had become a central component of the 11-year mandatory education initiative, supporting all aspects of the revolution, ideological, technological, and cultural. This system begins with creches available for children from birth to age 4, followed by kindergarten around age 4. North Koreans often compare their educational system, covering from kindergarten through university, which is free and compulsory, with those of other countries. This system was established in 1972. The sum mentioned represents the salary of a worker earning 130 won per month over a period of 10 years and 3 months.

Students attend kindergarten for one-year, elementary school for four years, middle school for six years, and many continue on to technical school or university. Besides the formal education system, there are highly effective and widespread nonformal and informal structures that support the Juche idea, which has become associated with North Korean Communism. Generally, the Korean term "Juche" means "self" or "subject." In the specific context of North Korean culture and politics, it refers to a modified version of Marxism and Leninism that emphasizes independence and self-reliance. The principle of Juche is crucial to

understanding education in North Korea, as it underpins the country's higher education institutions and is a major focus of scholarly research.

5. Benefits of the reunification of the Korean Peninsula

First, the foremost benefit is the elimination of the 'threat of war' between the two Koreas. Second, because they have the same Han ethnicity, they would emerge as a stronger nation. And rather than being a balancer to each other, they would result in a strong leader in the East Asian geo-politics. Ultimately, peace and tranquillity would prevail in the region.

Economy benefit

In the long run, the economic benefits of unifying Korea would be undeniable. By combining the North's natural resources and manpower with the South's well-established enterprises and conglomerates, massive economic opportunities may be created, raising Korea's worth and making it a significant worldwide power. Coal, iron ore, zinc, copper, and even gold are among North Korea's natural resources, three of which are used in the circuit boards of mobile phones. Combining them with items from LG, Samsung, and SK Hynix would almost certainly be successful.

Another issue to consider is both countries' social demography and population structures. Take note of how the ageing population in South Korea is more severe than in the North. This, combined with the South's low birth rate and the North's higher fertility rate, would result in a much more sustainable population in a united Korea. Securing a younger workforce in the future and, to some extent, preventing the looming ageing population catastrophe in many modern wealthy countries.

A 2017 poll found that South Koreans have different ideas about the benefits of unification. The most popular answer was that it would lower the risk of war (27.4%). Another 22% pointed to the economic opportunities that could arise from combining South Korea's advanced technology with North Korea's labor force. For 14.6% of respondents, easing the suffering of separated families was the key benefit, while 12.3% emphasized restoring the unity and identity of the Korean people.

Age differences revealed striking contrasts. Older South Koreans, particularly those in their 60s and above, placed greater importance on economic growth and the recovery of national identity. In contrast, younger South Koreans prioritized peace, with more than 30% of people in their 20s and 30s citing the elimination of war as the most important outcome of

unification. By comparing this, only 19% of respondents aged 60 and older shared this view.

The oldest people (17.6%) had the highest hopes when it came to national identity. Those in their 40s (15.3%) and 50s (13.9%) came in next. Among younger people, however, the sentiment was far weaker, with only 4.8% of those in their 20s and 6.6% of those in their 30s highlighting it as a major benefit. Taken together, the data suggest that younger South Koreans do not view unification as a matter of restoring shared ethnic identity. Instead, they see North Korea more as a security threat, valuing peace and stability over cultural or national homogeneity.

6. Conclusion

Undoubtedly, a unified Korea would definitely bring a paradigm shift in Geopolitics, not only in East Asian countries but in the whole world. It would certainly set an example for the rest of the world after Germany in the line of unification to bring peace and tranquillity to the region. It would surely bring a drastic change in the lives of North Korean people through better living standards and a better life, etc. Peace and tranquillity would prevail on the Korean peninsula. South Korea would support North Korea economically as a united Korea, which would ultimately improve the economic conditions of the people of North Korea, and it would result in a significant improvement in the quality of life.

Reunification would ultimately mean a new era for the Korean peninsula as a whole and a new era for world peace, as the unification also means a denuclearization of North Korea, and this energy would be utilised in some more constructive and fruitful way in nation-building. And denuclearization of the North has been one of the priorities towards world peace and tranquillity.

After 68 years of being split up, North and South Korea have very different ideas about who they are. A lot of young South Koreans find it hard to connect with the North because their government system, social norms, and culture are all very different. To bring people together, the South Korean government needs to actively support long-term social and cultural events that are more than just empty words and work toward real peace. Because integration is a long-term process, these initiatives should be framed not as short-term politics but as enduring policy commitments. Importantly, the younger generation must be persuaded of reunification's practical benefits through concrete evidence and reasoned arguments, rather than appeals based solely on nationalism.

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